

DETERMINING FACTORS FOR WELLBEING

Determining the ambient influences and configuration of optimised environments for emotional wellbeing of older adults

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ABSTRACT

It is now widely recognised that aspects such as tiredness or mood state can have an impact on an individual's wellbeing. However, there also exist other less studied factors that might be influential, and whose analysis is important to maximise personal wellbeing.

The aim of this study was to determine the influence of a set of 12 selected factors. Using the analysis of a 20-experiment case study by soft computing techniques the intention was to establish the most appropriate configuration for each factor to compose an optimal living environment to foster wellbeing.

The analysis revealed that ambient lighting and stress level are the factors that most impact emotional wellbeing. To a lesser extent, being able to take a break, ambient temperature and ambient noise play a relatively determining role.

The findings of this work can be used to establish a living environment for older persons that favours their emotional wellbeing.

Keywords: Built environment design, Ageing, Environmental ergonomic, User pleasure and emotion

Practitioner Summary:

This study analyses the level of influence of a set of ambient factors on the emotional wellbeing of older people, conducting, to this end, a series of controlled experiments, and concluding that ambient lighting and stress level are the factors most relevant to promote a better living environment.

INTRODUCTION

In any activity, the ambient factors around a person can have an effect on performance and outcome. For this reason, evaluating the influence of certain ambient parameters on an individual's mood or mental state is a research area of great interest (Martin et al., 2019; Bravo et al., 2016; Castillo et al., 2016; Fernández-Caballero et al., 2016). Most studies, however, focus on testing whether a well-known and widely accepted set of factors have a determining influence on the performance of a specific task, while attaching little importance to understanding the actual level of the impact depending on other circumstances.

Thus, the aim of the present study was to determine the significance of a set of selected ambient factors during the performance of a specific task: the emotional interpretation and evaluation of a set of images taken from the International Affective Picture System (IAPS) (Lang et al., 2008), designed as a standardised tool for use by researchers studying emotion and attention. The intention of determining the degree of influence is to apply this knowledge to create environments that foster wellbeing in older adults considering said well-being as a better feeling regarding factors such as valence, arousal and dominance.

To conduct this study, we selected a set of 12 factors, such as ambient temperature, presence or absence of noise, wall colour and level of lighting, which can be easily regulated in any environment. By combining different settings for such factors, we created various environments in which a series of 20 experiments were conducted with a group of individuals of similar characteristics (age, health status, education, etc.), who were asked to perform a simple task involving looking at a set of images of different categories and using a scale to rate the emotion each one evoked. However, establishing the level of influence of each of these factors is complex when they are combined to configure different situations. To solve this problem, we used various soft computing techniques, such as dendrograms, CART-type decision trees, influence diagrams and rule extraction algorithms.

Related work

Currently, one of the main areas of research in human psychology is the analysis of the influence of ambient factors on people, yet few works have focused on older population groups.

Studies conducted in academic settings, such as those by Yildirim et al. (2014) and Lee et al. (2020), have attempted to analyse the influence of colour or ventilation (Maula et al., 2016) in classrooms on students' wellbeing.

Important works have studied behaviours in adults, albeit in work environments, aiming to determine the factors that encourage greater productivity or reduce mental stress (Alyan et al., 2020). In the same line, reviews such as that conducted by Jalil et al. (2012) and works developed in different environments (Kwallek et al., 1988; Öztürk et al., 2011; Lee et al., 2018), focus on the analysis of how the colour of walls affects mood or productivity.

Also using a sample of adults, a number of works have studied the influence of artificial ambient lighting (Kort & Smolders, 2010; Yu & Akita, 2019; Vries et al., 2020), natural light (Court et al., 2010), temperature (Wang et al., 2013), and also illumination and temperature in conjunction (Adhvaryu et al., 2019; Vimalanathan & Ramesh Babu, 2014), reporting their significant effect on behaviour and wellbeing. From a more architectural perspective, a number of works address the aspects of buildings that promote wellbeing (Tuckett et al., 2018), looking at elements such as window size (Yeom et al., 2020). Additionally, researchers including Lawrence et al. (2019) and Koehler et al. (2018) have studied the relationship between contact with nature and healthy environments and the effect on physical and mental health. In the context of the interpretation of visual stimuli, noteworthy works include that by Bradley et al. (2007), which assesses how a group of individuals interpret sets of visual stimuli, and other studies comparing the differences in responses between young and older adults (Fernández-Aguilar et al., 2020; McManis et al., 2001) or men and women (Bradley et al., 2001; Lungu et al., 2015).

Finally, and focusing on studies with older population, works such as those by Castillo et al. (2016) and Fernández-Caballero et al. (2016) use sensors to monitor the facial and gestural expressions, physiological parameters, activity and behaviour of older adults, with the aim of recognising their emotions, analysing how music, colour and light are able to induce a positive, pleasant mood state. Additionally, works such as the study by McCaffrey (2009) analyse the effect of music on cognition in older adults undergoing surgery or palliative care (Wood et al., 2019), while Belgrave (2011) compares its effect on children and older adults. In addition, in the field of physical factors, it is worth noting studies like that by Gobbens & Van Assen (2018), where the authors analyse the influence of the immediate environment around a home (neighbourhood, public institutions, traffic, etc.), and that by Lucas & Lawless (2013), which examines the effect of good weather on health.

Table 1 summarises a selection of works related to the objective of the present study.

Table 1

Related work

Study	Setting	Factors	Age group	Data processing method
Yildirim, 2014	Academic	Colour	Young people	Statistical methods
Lee et al., 2020	Academic	Colour	Young people	Mathematical and statistical methods
Maula et al., 2016	Academic	Ventilation	Young people	Statistical methods
Kwallek et al., 1988	Business	Colour	Adults	Mathematical and statistical methods
Öztürk, 2011	Business	Colour	Adults	Statistical methods
Lee et al, 2019	General	Colour	Adults	Statistical methods
Kort & Smolders, 2010	Business	Lighting	Adults	Statistical methods
Yu & Akita, 2019	Business	Lighting	Adults	Statistical methods

Vries et al., 2020	Business	Lighting	Adults	Statistical methods
Wang, 2013	Business	Temperature	Adults	Multi-agents methods
Adhvaryu et al., 2019	Business	Lighting and temperature	Adults	Mathematical and statistical methods
Vimalanathan & Ramesh Babu, 2014	Business	Lighting and temperature	Adults	Neurobehavioral test (NBT) and statistical methods
Yeom, 2020	Business	Ventilation	Adults	Mathematical and statistical methods
Bradley et al., 2017	General	Colour	Adults	Statistical methods
Castillo et al., 2016	General	Music, colour and lighting	Older adults	Computational methods
Fernández-Caballero et al., 2016	General	Music, colour and lighting	Older adults	Computational and machine learning methods
McCaffrey, 2009	Hospital	Music	Older adults	Statistical methods
Wood et al., 2019	Hospital	Music	Older adults	Statistical methods
Belgrave, 2011	General	Music	Young and older adults	Statistical methods
Lucas & Lawless, 2013	General	Weather	Older adults	Computational and machine learning methods

As can be seen, numerous studies in recent years have focused on determining how exposure to different ambient stimuli is interpreted depending on variables such as age or gender. Important research has also been conducted on establishing how controlling certain factors, such as light, colour or temperature, can affect productivity in the workplace. However, the analysis of a broader set of ambient factors and the extent of their impact, using soft computing techniques, is a field in which research is hitherto scant, especially with the aim of helping older adults, as is the purpose of the present work.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

To determine which ambient factors have a greater impact on individuals while performing a task, a model was designed using data from various controlled experiments and soft computing techniques. Figure 1 shows a flow diagram of the proposed process.

Figure 1 Caption: General flow diagram

Figure 1 Alt Text: Representation of the order and relationships of the different phases that make up the proposed method: selection of participants, conducting experiments, processing of generated data, extraction of knowledge and decision-making to establish a coexistence environment where well-being is favored

The actors involved and the stages conducted are described as follows.

Participants

To conduct the experiments, we recruited ten volunteers (50% women) without significant epidemiological differences, and whose ages ranged from 71 to 83 years (M=75.8,

SD=4.13). Half the participants presented chronic pathologies with no effect on their cognitive capacity and ability to participate in the experiments. During the experiments, in which certain conditions of light, temperature, background music, etc., were simulated, the participants were required to evaluate, using specific scales, the impression produced on observing different sets of photos.

This research complied with the recommendations of Agreement 06/2016 of the Clinical Research Ethics Committee (CREC) and was approved by the Clinical Research Ethics Committee of the Castilla-La Mancha Health Service. Informed consent was obtained from each participant.

Procedure

To configure the different environments in which to conduct the experiments, a set of 12 factors was selected. The factors corresponded to the different parameters whose influence was analysed during the performance of the selected task, namely the evaluation of sensations generated by exposure to pictures. The participants were already aware of some of these factors (e.g. the time the experiment was to be conducted or the temperature in the room) and others were unexpected or previously unknown (presence, or not, of drink food or existence of noise). Each of these factors is described as follows.

- Time: when the experiment was conducted.
- Lighting: artificial lighting, of different intensities, was used.
- Ambient temperature: the temperature was set using heating/cooling devices.
- Background music: a music player was used to provide different types of music.
- Interruptions: a number of planned interruptions.
- Colour of walls: depending on the room where the experiment was conducted.
- Food and/or drink: presence or absence of food and/or drink.
- Weather: the outside weather during the experiment.

- Noise: presence or absence of people talking in the room.
- Rest: possibility, or not, of taking a break.
- Reward: in some experiments, participants were informed of the possibility of a symbolic reward as an incentive.
- Stress: simulated by setting, or not, a time limit.

Table 2 shows the different values for the selected ambient factors.

Table 2

Ambient factors and the values used

External factors	Possible values		
F1: Time	1: Morning (9.00h)	2: Afternoon (15.00h)	3: Evening (19:00)
F2: Lighting	1: Bright	2: Medium	3: Low
F3: Ambient temperature	1: Hot (28°C)	2: Comfortable (21°C)	3: Cool (18°C)
F4: Background music	1: No music	2: Classical music	3: Pop music
F5: Interruptions	1: No interruptions	2: Some interruptions	3: Many interruptions
F6: Colour of walls	1: White	2: Blue	3: Combination
F7: Food and/or drink	1: Nothing	2: Only water	3: Food and water
F8: Weather	1: Sunny	2: Cloudy	3: Rainy
F9: Noise	1: No noise	2: One person	3: Several people
F10: Rest	1: No break	2: One break	3: Several breaks
F11: Reward	1: No reward	2: A possible reward	3: A reward
F12: Stress	1: No time limit	2: Tight time limit	3: Insufficient time

By combining several values for each of the parameters, it is possible to define different environments for each experiment. Thus, Table 6 shows the combination established for the 20 experiments developed in the case study.

Measures

Each time a volunteer observed a picture, they were asked to rate the emotion it evoked with relation to three pairs of feelings:

- Happy vs. Unhappy (valence).
- Calm vs. Excited (arousal).
- Controlled vs. In control (dominance).

To simplify the rating for each picture, the volunteers were given a scale for each pair of emotions, using manikins (Lang, Bradley, & Cuthbert, 2008).

Figure 2 Caption: Scale for rating emotions

Figure 2 Alt Text: Three scales to assess, from 1 to 9, the perceived sensation for each pair of emotions: valence, arousal and dominance

The participants used a pen to mark an X at the corresponding point on the scale from 1 to 9 (Figure 3).

Figure 3 Caption: Possible scores for each emotion

Figure 3 Alt Text: Scale for valuation of valence, showing the 9 possible values

A score close to 1 on the first pair of emotions (valence) expresses a high degree of unhappiness, while a score close to 9 means great happiness. A low score on the second pair (arousal) represents excitement while the higher scores express calm. Finally, a low score in the third pair of emotions (dominance) represents feeling overcome by the situation, while a high score suggests the participant feels in control in response to the stimulus.

Data analysis procedure: Soft Computing

After preparing the participants and configuring the different environments, we conducted the experiments. The different phases required are described as follows.

Processing and homogenisation

During the experiments, each participant completed a response sheet with their rating of the emotion evoked by each image, following the format shown in Table 3.

Table 3

Individual rating sheet

Picture	Rating		
	Valence	Arousal	Dominance
Pic1			
Pic2			
⋮			
Pic60			

In this processing and homogenisation phase, the results were revised individually to detect possible inconsistencies or errors. In addition, the values were scaled to homogenize them and establish them in a common scale.

Generation of datasets

After checking the individual response sheets, a dataset was generated for each of the 20 experiments, following the structure shown in Table 4. These data formed the basis on which to begin the process of analysis and knowledge extraction.

Table 4*Dataset of results per experiment (for Experiment 1, in this case)*

Experiment	Participant	Picture	Valence	Arousal	Dominance
Exp1	P1	Pic1			
Exp1	P1	Pic2			
Exp1	P1	⋮			
Exp1	P1	Pic60			
Exp1	P2	Pic1			
Exp1	P2	Pic2			
Exp1	P2	⋮			
Exp1	P2	Pic60			
⋮	⋮	⋮			
Exp1	P10	Pic1			
Exp1	P10	Pic2			
Exp1	P10	⋮			
Exp1	P10	Pic60			

Knowledge extraction

The aim of this phase was to discover which factors had the greatest effect on the emotional interpretation of visual stimuli. To this end, we applied different soft computing techniques: dendrograms to obtain the first classification of the experimental results, similarity matrices, CART-type decision trees to determine the parameters with the greatest impact, influence diagrams for easy viewing and association rule extraction for pattern discovery.

The knowledge extraction process is carried out by executing four steps, in which different techniques are combined. Table 5 shows the phases carried out.

Table 5*Knowledge extraction and analysis process*

Action	Goal	Technique	Algorithm/Platform	Result
1	Generate clusters of experiments based on their result	Unsupervised learning algorithm: clustering	Hierarchical clustering: agglomerative dendrogram	Division of the 20 experiments into 3 groups, according to their results

2	Obtain level of influence of the factors evaluated in the results obtained	Supervised learning algorithm: classification	Decision Tree CART 4.5 developed in Python and executed in Spyder IDE 4.1	List of influencing factors, and influence value, on the results of the experiments
3	Graphically visualize the influence relationships between factors and results	Unsupervised learning influence diagram	Influence diagram developed in Python and executed in Spyder IDE 4.1	Diagram for easy visualization of influence relationships
4	Obtain association rules between the configuration of the factors and the results of the experiments	Unsupervised Learning Algorithm: Association Rules Extraction	“Magnum Opus” type association extraction algorithm executed on BigML	Relevant associations between the values of the evaluated factors and the results of the experiments

The description of the case study includes a detailed account of all these techniques.

Decision-making

From the knowledge obtained, a representation of the level of influence of each of the environmental factors analyzed is generated. Knowing the factors with the greatest effect on each individual’s emotional interpretation enables the appropriate decisions to be made to establish living conditions that provide the greatest wellbeing.

Repeating the experiments in ideal conditions and reporting the results

Having established the ideal environment, which combines the optimal values for the factors determined to be the most influential, we conducted a final experiment, with the aim of evaluating whether, and to what extent, the best outcomes are achieved.

RESULTS

The aim of this case study was to expose the participants to a set of pictures of various categories and to assess how their responses varied according to the different ambient factors.

The experimental phases are described as follows

Selection of images

To conduct the experiments, we used the set of 1200 images in the International Affective Picture System (IAPS) (Lang et al., 2008), developed and distributed by the International Institute of Mental Health Centre for Emotion and Attention at the University of Florida. This collection of pictures contains photographs from a range of categories (happy people, landscapes, scenes of violence, etc.) designed to evoke different emotions. Given that the set comprises 1200 pictures and the study consisted of 20 experiments, the photographs were divided into 20 groups of 60 pictures.

Preparation of participants

Before beginning the experiments, the participants were explained the conditions under which they would be conducted. They were also offered the possibility of not scoring pictures they might find offensive. They gave their signed informed consent and authorised the anonymous disclosure of the results.

Preparation of environments

Taking into account the factors and their possible values presented in Table 2, we conducted 20 experiments combining different values for these factors. The combination was generated randomly so as to maintain the independence of the factors and values, ensuring a sufficiently uniform combination of the values of each factor. Table 6 shows the conditions under which the experiments were conducted.

Table 6*Experiments programmed*

Experiment	Value for each factor											
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12
Exp0	1	1	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	3	3	1
Exp1	1	3	1	1	2	1	1	3	2	1	3	3
Exp2	1	1	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	3	1	1
Exp3	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	2	3	1	1
Exp4	1	3	3	2	2	1	3	2	1	2	3	3
Exp5	1	1	2	1	1	2	2	1	1	3	1	1
Exp6	1	2	3	1	1	3	3	3	1	2	1	2
Exp7	1	2	3	1	1	1	3	1	2	2	2	2
Exp8	1	2	3	1	1	3	3	1	3	2	1	2
Exp9	2	3	1	3	3	1	1	1	2	1	2	3
Exp10	2	1	2	1	1	2	2	1	1	3	2	2
Exp11	2	1	2	3	1	3	2	2	1	2	3	1
Exp12	2	2	1	3	3	2	1	1	3	1	2	3
Exp13	2	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	2	2	3	1
Exp14	2	2	3	2	2	1	3	1	3	2	3	2
Exp15	3	2	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	3	2
Exp16	3	3	1	3	2	1	1	1	3	1	1	2
Exp17	3	1	2	1	1	3	2	2	2	3	2	1
Exp18	3	3	1	1	1	3	1	3	2	1	1	3
Exp19	3	2	3	1	1	1	3	1	1	1	3	2

Allocation of experiments

The 10 participants were distributed across the 20 experiments in such a way that each experiment was conducted with at least 4 participants. Table 7 shows the allocation.

Table 7*Allocation of experiments*

Experiment	Participant									
	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10
Exp0	X	X						X	X	X
Exp1			X	X				X	X	X
Exp2	X	X	X	X						
Exp3			X	X				X	X	X
Exp4	X	X			X	X	X			
Exp5			X	X				X	X	
Exp6					X	X	X			X
Exp7	X	X						X	X	

Exp8	X	X						X	X	
Exp9			X	X				X	X	
Exp10					X	X	X			X
Exp11	X	X	X	X						X
Exp12					X	X	X			X
Exp13	X	X						X	X	X
Exp14	X	X	X	X						
Exp15					X	X	X			X
Exp16					X	X	X			X
Exp17	X	X						X	X	
Exp18			X	X	X	X	X			
Exp19			X	X	X	X	X			

Thus, no participant repeated the task more than ten times and at least 4 participants were involved in each experiment. The average time involved in performing each experiment was 22 minutes, thus requiring a mean participation of 200 minutes per volunteer.

Data collection and processing

Before conducting the experiments, the participants were explained how to rate the sensations they felt on viewing the images. Each picture had to be rated according to the three affective dimensions: valence, arousal and dominance.

Table 8 shows an extract from the results of the first experiment.

Table 8

Results of first experiment

Participant	Picture ID	Valence	Arousal	Dominance
P1	Pic1	7	6	8
	Pic2	5	4	3
	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
	Pic60	8	8	9
P2	Pic1	8	7	7
	Pic2	6	4	2
	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
	Pic60	7	7	8
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
P10	Pic1	8	9	8
	Pic2	4	6	6
	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
	Pic60	7	7	6

After the 20 experiments, the participants' mean scores were calculated, thus obtaining an overall rating on each dimension for each experiment.

Table 9

Experimental results

Experiment	Valence	Arousal	Dominance
Exp0	8.11	6.86	6.55
Exp1	4.83	4.26	4.60
Exp2	7.23	7.14	7.68
Exp3	6.93	7.11	7.96
Exp4	5.91	5.35	4.39
Exp5	6.62	7.23	8.03
Exp6	6.21	5.42	6.05
Exp7	6.14	5.39	6.16
Exp8	6.11	5.79	5.47
Exp9	4.98	5.17	4.86
Exp10	7.59	7.44	6.78
Exp11	7.36	7.35	7.20
Exp12	5.15	4.35	4.12
Exp13	6.47	7.41	4.72
Exp14	6.14	6.15	4.58
Exp15	6.31	5.20	5.65
Exp16	3.81	4.91	4.31
Exp17	6.55	7.58	6.86
Exp18	4.42	5.29	4.40
Exp19	4.62	5.90	6.15

Selection of the most influential factors

A hierarchic clustering algorithm was applied to the data in Table 9, from which we obtained a dendrogram. We then calculated the distance between clusters using a “farthest neighbour” method to generate homogeneous groups of values.

Figure 4 Caption: Dendrogram

Figure 4 Alt Text: Classification of the 20 experiments in 3 groups according to their results

The dendrogram reveals three considerably homogeneous clusters following the ratings obtained for each pair of emotions. The first cluster, categorised as experiments with a “bad” result is that composed of the experiments with the lowest scores for the three dimensions: Exp5, Exp2, Exp3, Exp11, Exp17 and Exp0. The second cluster, which we called “moderate”, comprising the experiments with medium ratings: Exp15, Exp6, Exp7, Exp13, Exp19, Exp8 and Exp14. Finally, the third cluster, which we called “good”, included the experiments that scored highest on positive emotions: Exp4, Exp9, Exp16, Exp18, Exp1 and Exp12.

Table 10

Classification of experiments

Good	Moderate	Bad
Exp0	Exp6	Exp1
Exp2	Exp7	Exp4
Exp3	Exp8	Exp9
Exp5	Exp13	Exp12
Exp10	Exp14	Exp16
Exp11	Exp15	Exp18
Exp17	Exp19	

Once the different groups were obtained, the aim was to determine the factors with the

greatest impact. For this purpose, a decision tree analysis was performed. Figure 5 shows a decision tree generated from the classification obtained using the dendrogram. To build this, we applied an extension of the Cart decision tree algorithm (Breiman et al., 1984; Lungu et al., 2015), using statistical pruning to reduce the risk of overlearning.

Figure 5 Caption: Pruned decision tree

Figure 5 Alt Text: Decision tree, with pruning, generated from the results of the characteristics of each experiment and its result. Factors F2, F12 and F3 are the most relevant

The decision tree shows that all the experiments in which F2 has a value of 1 or less (that is, strong lighting), are classified in the “good” group”, while when F2 has a value of more than 1 (medium or low lighting), it is necessary to check the value of F12 to classify the result. Specifically, when F12 has a value of more than 2 (insufficient time), the result is categorised as “bad”, However, if the value of F12 is 2 or less (no deadline or tight deadline), it is necessary to refer to the value of F3, which, if above 2 (cool ambient temperature), the result is “moderate” or “bad”.

To verify the quality of the results obtained from the decision tree shown in Figure 5,

we estimated the most significant metrics, comparing the classification generated by the decision tree with the actual classification of each experiment. This enabled us to determine whether the decision tree results were sufficiently robust to accept the classification and thus the classifying powers of the factors selected and included in the tree.

The metrics used to evaluate the results of the decision tree classification were as follows:

- Accuracy: ratio of correctly predicted observations to the total of performed observations.
- Precision: ratio of correctly predicted positive observations to the total predicted positive observations.
- Recall: ratio of correctly predicted positive observations to all observations in a specific class.
- F-Measure: this is the balanced harmonic mean of Recall and Precision, giving both metrics equal weight.

Table 11

Pruned tree metrics

Actual Vs Predicted	Good	Bad	Fair	Actual	Accuracy	Recall	Precision	F-Measure
Good	7	0	0	7	95%	100%	87.5%	0.93
Bad	0	6	0	6	95%	100%	100%	1
Fair	1	0	6	7	100%	85.71%	100%	0.92
Predicted	8	6	6	20	96.67	95.24%	95.83%	0.95
					AVG.	AVG.	AVG.	AVG.
					Accuracy	Recall	Precision	F-Measure

According to the data in Table 11, although the performance could be considered relatively good, it can be seen that one of the experiments catalogued as “moderate” was not correctly classified, and hence an unpruned decision tree was generated (Figure 6).

Figure 6 Caption: Unpruned decision tree (confidence 100%)

Figure 6 Alt Text: Decision tree, without pruning and with maximum confidence, generated from the results of the characteristics of each experiment and its result. Factors F2, F10, F12, F9 and F3 are the most relevant

The resulting tree is more complex than the previous one, but the metrics present excellent values.

Table 12

Unpruned tree metrics

Actual Vs Predicted	Good	Bad	Fair	Actual	Accuracy	Recall	Precision	F-Measure
Good	7	0	0	7	100%	100%	100%	1
Bad	0	6	0	6	100%	100%	100%	1
Fair	0	0	7	7	100%	100%	100%	1
Predicted	7	6	7	20	100%	100%	100%	1
					AVG.	AVG.	AVG.	AVG.
					Accuracy	Recall	Precision	F-Measure

Additionally, given that interpreting the resulting tree might have been complex, the influence diagram shown in Figure 7 was generated to facilitate the visualisation of the most significant factors.

Figure 7 Caption: Influence diagram

Figure 7 Alt Text: Influence relationships between the selected factors and the classification obtained for the results of the experiments

The influence diagram depicts the factors involved and their interrelationships, showing that Factors 2, 12, 10, 3 and 9 are the most influential. The other factors were discarded. To quantify the degree of influence of each factor, Figure 8 shows the percentage of significance obtained in generating the decision tree.

Figure 8 Caption: Significance of each factor

Figure 8 Alt Text: Representation of the level of influence of each selected factor. The results obtained show the following order: F2, F12, F10, F3 and F9

These results show that F2 has the greatest classifying power, followed by F12, while F10, F3 and F3 have some significance, but to a lesser extent.

Determining the best environment

To determine the optimum values for each of the five factors found to be the most influential, association rule mining was performed. To this end, we used the algorithm proposed by Webb (2011), which was introduced into the BigML machine learning platform (The BigML Team, 2020). A total of 12 rules resulted from applying the algorithm.

Table 13

Association rules

ID	Rule	Support	Coverage	Confidence	Leverage	Lift
R0	$F2 \leq 1 \rightarrow 1 < F3 \leq 2$	40%	40%	100 %	24 %	2.5
R1	$1 < F3 \leq 2 \rightarrow F2 \leq 1$	40%	40%	100 %	24 %	2.5
R2	$1 < F3 \leq 2 \rightarrow \text{label}=\text{Good}$	35%	40%	87.5%	21 %	2.5
R3	$C=\text{Good} \rightarrow 1 < F3 \leq 2$	35%	35%	100 %	21 %	2.5
R4	$F2 \leq 1 \rightarrow F12 \leq 1$	35%	40%	87.5%	21 %	2.5
R5	$F12 \leq 1 \rightarrow F2 \leq 1$	35%	35%	100 %	21 %	2.5
R6	$F12 \leq 1 \rightarrow 1 < F3 \leq 2$	35%	35%	100 %	21 %	2.5
R7	$F2 \leq 1 \rightarrow \text{label}=\text{Good}$	35%	40%	87.5%	21 %	2.5
R8	$C=\text{Good} \rightarrow F2 \leq 1$	35%	35%	100 %	21 %	2.5
R9	$1 < F3 \leq 2 \rightarrow F12 \leq 1$	35%	40%	87.5%	21%	2.5
R10	$F10 > 2 \rightarrow \text{label}=\text{Good}$	30%	30%	100 %	19.5%	2.9
R11	$C=\text{Good} \rightarrow F10 > 2$	30%	35%	85.7%	19.5%	2.9

The discovery of association rule concentrates on detecting relationships between values rather than variables. An association rule is defined as an implication of the form “if X, then Y” ($X \rightarrow Y$), where X would be the antecedent or left-hand-side (LHS) and Y the consequent or right-hand-side (RHS). The parameters used to evaluate the quality and significance of the rules extracted are as follows:

- Coverage: the support of the antecedent of an association rule, i.e., the portion of instances in the dataset that contain the antecedent itemset. It measures how often a rule can be applied.
- Support: the percentage of instances that contain the rule's antecedent and rule's consequent together over the total number of instances.

- Confidence: the percentage of instances that contain the consequent and antecedent together over the number of instances that only contain the antecedent.
- Leverage: the difference between the probability of the rule and the expected probability if the items were statistically independent.
- Lift: how many times more often antecedent and consequent occur together than expected if they were statistically independent.

As shown in Table 13, although it is possible to extract 12 rules, the ones of greatest interest to determine the optimal values of the influential factors are those in which the antecedent or consequent is the classification of the experiment (“good”, “bad” or “moderate”). Thus, as Figure 9 shows, the useful rules are R1, R2, R7, R8 and R11.

Figure 9 Caption: Association rules (leverage 19.5%)

Figure 9 Alt Text: Spatial visualization of the selected association rules considering the quality metrics obtained

In light of the above, we obtained optimal values for F2, F3 and F10. The association rules extracted for F9 and F12 lacked sufficient, although analysing the results of the experiments and the configuration of F9 and F12, the values that provide the best results were found to be 1 (no noise) for F9 and 2 (comfortable temperature) for F12.

Table 14*Optimal values*

Factor	Optimal value
F2: Light	1: Bright
F10: Rest	3: Several breaks
F12: Stress	1: No time limit
F9: Noise	1: No noise
F3: Ambient temperature	2: Comfortable (21°C)

Repetition of experiment in an optimised environment

Once the most influential factors and their optimal values had been determined, we prepared a new environment combining both to configure the ideal environment. A final experiment was conducted, following the same previously described steps, with the results shown in Table 15.

Table 15

Ratings in an ideal environment

Participant	Picture	Valence	Arousal	Dominance
P1	Pic1	9	7	8
	Pic2	8	9	7
	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
	Pic60	9	8	9
P2	Pic1	6	8	8
	Pic2	7	9	9
	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
	Pic60	8	9	9
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
P10	Pic1	8	9	8
	Pic2	9	7	7
	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
	Pic60	8	7	8

After processing the data obtained for each participant, finding the aggregate and the mean score, we obtained the results shown in Table 16.

Table 16

Mean values in an optimised environment

Experiment	Valence	Arousal	Dominance
New experiment (optimal environment)	7.89	7.84	8.03

The values generated in this final experiment, with the optimal configuration of the most influential factors, were clearly better than the mean scores for the previous 20 experiments.

Table 17

Mean values in previous experiments

Experiment	Valence	Arousal	Dominance
“Good” experiments	7.20	7.24	7.29
“Moderate” experiments	6.00	5.89	5.54
“Bad” experiments	4.85	4.89	4.45

Finally, the image in Figure 10 shows a comparative three-dimensional representation of the results obtained in the experiments conducted.

Figure 10 Caption: Results of experiments conducted vs optimal conditions

Figure 10 Alt Text: Visual comparison of the results obtained in the new experiment with respect to the previous 20. The new result is significantly better

The results obtained in the final experiment (optimal parameterisation) presents better values in the three dimensions under analysis, that is, the three pairs of emotions considered.

DISCUSSION

Determining the degree of the impact of specific factors on older adults' wellbeing is an interesting challenge and field of study in various scientific disciplines. In this work, we modelled and conducted a set of experiments, whose results were processed and analysed using different soft computing techniques, which proved effective in quantifying the influence of each of the selected factors. The results underline the importance of five of these factors, discarding the others. The analysis established the optimal values of each of these five factors to configure an environment that favoured the greatest possible emotional wellbeing.

Table 18

Significance and optimal values of the most influential factors

Factor	Significance	Optimal value
F2: Lighting	58.44%	1: Bright
F10: Rest	22.18%	3: Several breaks
F12: Stress	8.04%	1: No time limit
F9: Noise	7.65%	1: No noise
F3: Ambient temperature	3.70%	2: Comfortable (21°C)

Our data suggest, firstly, that lighting is a clearly influential factor (58.44%), as reported in other works (Kort & Smolders, 2010), confirming that the presence of a strong source of bright light is directly related to a greater sensation of comfort and wellbeing. It is important to note that our experiments used artificial lighting, without taking into account colour temperature and natural light, effects analysed by Yu & Akita (2019) and Court et al. (2010).

Secondly, taking breaks while performing tasks (in this case the emotional interpretation of pictures), also has a significant impact (22.18%). Although no studies were found that corroborate or contradict this finding, it is interesting to note that the third most influential factor was stress (8.04%), simulated in this case by giving participants a set time to complete the task. Despite these two factors being modelled and processed independently,

stress and rest are evidently related elements, which is arguably why the results show both to be influential factors.

The fourth most influential factor is ambient noise (7.65%), the absence of which promotes wellbeing. This finding is partially corroborated by works such as those by McCaffrey (2009) and Belgrave (2011), where the impact of noise is analysed with the conclusion that low volume music, which does not disturb or hinder concentration, is especially beneficial for older adults.

Finally, the fifth factor is ambient temperature, which presents a relative influence (3.70%), with a comfortable level (21°C) being found to encourage a feeling of wellbeing. Studies such as those Kort & Smolders (2010) and Court et al. (2010), albeit conducted in business settings and assessing the effect on employees, confirm this finding.

The other factors were discarded as they were found to have little effect, taking into account the limitation of the set of experiments conducted and the sample size. In the groups of factors found to be statistically non-significant, it is worth noting that of the colour of the walls, given that previous research has focused on its impact (Kwallek et al., 1988; Yildirim, 2014), reporting a certain degree of influence of colour tones on perceived wellbeing. Despite this apparent contradiction, it should be noted that the colours used in our experiments (blue, white and combined) were, in all cases, light or very light. This might justify our results and bring them more into line with those of the cited studies.

It is important to point out as a limitation of the study, in addition to the size of the number of participants, the fact that no one from a different age group was included, which would have allowed us to obtain age-specific results. In addition, it is also necessary to consider that the participation of each volunteer for about 200 total minutes as a sum of their intervention in the different experiments (an important interval) could have influenced the capacities and level of performance of each one, as well as in the results obtained. However, having carried

out the experiments on different days, never exceeding their daily participation in more than 30 minutes, it is expected that the influence of this factor has been limited.

The knowledge obtained on the level of influence of the factors analysed in this work may be used to configure improve living environments, which are able to provide greater wellbeing. This was confirmed by our repeating the experiment under the optimal conditions found in the study, revealing an improvement of 29.98%, 29.37%, 37.73%, respectively, in the three dimensions under analysis (“happy/unhappy”, “calm/excited”, “controlled/in control”) compared to the first set of 20 experiments conducted.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a set of experiments was conducted, in different simulated environments, with the aim of determining the ambient factors with the greatest impact on the emotional wellbeing of older adults. The experiments and the data analysis revealed that the two most influential factors were ambient lighting and the level of stress while performing the task. Three other factors, the possibility of taking breaks, ambient temperature and ambient noise, were also found to be influential, albeit to a lesser extent. These findings were used to configure an environment to encourage emotional wellbeing, the effectiveness of which was confirmed.

KEY POINTS

- Older adults’ emotional interpretation of pictures depends on the environment and ambient factors.
- Ambient factors, such as lighting and stress, have a significant, positive effect on visual interpretation of stimuli and greater wellbeing.
- The use of soft computing techniques facilitates the quantification of the influence of factors affecting emotional wellbeing.

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